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A DIFFERENT APPROACH TO THE IMPACT OF IMMIGRATION ON HOUSING PRICES

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Abstract

It is the most correct approach to evaluate the increase in the prices of the houses together with the new houses, the number of which is increasing every day in our country. Although the acceleration in housing construction is related to political and political decisions, the housing sector needs academic studies, especially in terms of migration. In this study, we tried to underline that it is necessary to examine my “migration concept” as one of the factors that decide housing prices and that it needs much more literature contribution. We believe that, rather than acting on the assumption that it is natural for an increase in housing prices due to demand, it is correct to process the results of the factors that create the relevant demand with data and analysis. It is obvious that another concept that can be considered at the macro level should be considered separately, as the problem of residence, housing and migration, which arose due to the refugees coming to Turkey due to the war in the Syrian Arab Republic, brought an additional burden to the housing shortage at hand. In examining and solving the problems related to the effect of migration, literature reviews and analyses, panel data analyzes, stata applications together with the econometric model will supply a literature contribution. Although the investments made by the public sector supply suppressive effects on housing prices from time to time , it would be correct to give examples from different regions, especially Istanbul, to examine these and similar effects.

Keywords: *Migration, Housing Prices, Effect of Migration on Housing Prices, Increase in Housing Prices, Relationship between Migration and Housing*

Introduction

The value given to the construction sector, due to the growth policies that Turkey had to enter, especially at the beginning of the 200's, led to an increase in discussions on housing production and unit prices. In the early days, especially for the Turkish economy, the policies that will have side effects later formed the determinants of housing prices. The global migrant stock was from 72 million to 243 million, respectively, between 1960 and 2015 (World Bank, 2018). Three percent of the world's population are now immigrants. Relevant issues are of interest to researchers from many disciplines, including medicine, economics, and sociology (Abramitzky and Boustan , 2017; Hassan, 2017). Migration has become one of the most pressing socials, economic and political issues generating heated debate in countries facing large flows of migrants (Saiz and Wachter , 2011; Accreturo et al., 2014; Abramitzky and Boustan , 2017). A particular focus of this discussion is the impact of immigration on house prices. While researchers claim that immigration reduces house prices, some argue otherwise (Sá , 2015; Mussa et al., 2017). Immigration increases the demand for housing and rental accommodation, but these can also affect their impact and the perceived desire of the neighborhoods involved (Acetturo et al., 2014). Social interactions between locals and foreigners are particularly important (SAIZ and WACHTER, 2011; Acetturo et al., 2014; Sá , 2015). Research shows that immigration affects house prices depending on their level.

In terms of literature

it would be correct to explain the change in the form of rent in Ricardo , which continues with Smith's discussion of rent, as follows:

If it were possible for all lands to have the same characteristics, even if the lands were not in an incredibly special and favorable position due to the unlimited quantity and quality of the lands, no bill could be made against the use of the land. In this case, the result is that the lands are not unlimited in quantity and of the same quality; Again, due to the increase in the population, lands of lower quality or less favorable conditions are also opened for cultivation, and rent is paid in return for the use of the land. In terms of the progress and fertility of the society, the cultivation of second-class lands leads to the payment of rent on first-class lands; this results in the determination of the amount of the rent depending on the quality difference between the two lands in question. (Ricardo , 2008: 46).

In small local housing markets, immigration can increase house prices by directly increasing demand. Alternatively, house prices may fall. Indirect local resident emigration and (Saiz and Wachter , 2011; Sá , 2015; Mussa et al., 2017) or house prices grow at a slow rate, the area is considered less desirable. In larger areas, direct demand effects may remain, while indirect effects are likely to be silenced (SAIZ, 2007).

Marx's use of the concept of ground rent , which also uses the differential rent analysis put forward by Ricardo , are still alive today. (Yakar Önal, 2002). Our present study reveals that it is necessary to compile the findings from the first comprehensive meta-regression analysis to assess the conflicting demands about immigration and house prices. Specifically, it is necessary to explore two related issues:

(i) *Does immigration affect house prices?*

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(ii) *Is this effect moderate in terms of attitudes of local populations towards immigrants? Although the individual study tried to answer; Similar studies do not appear in the literature.*

Beliefs and attitudes play a critical role in nearly all market transactions, and attitudes can be central to willingness to pay (Bowles , 1998; Frey , 1999). Consequently, it is necessary to assume this in the case where the local population is at the destination.

Global Perspective

Countries are accepting more immigrants; it is obvious that the increased demand for housing from immigrants will increase house prices. This is not necessarily driven by emigration, of course. Indeed, there may still be a net movement to one geographic area, but people are not prepared to pay as much as other areas due to migration. This moderating role for immigrants in relation to these local attitudes has not been explored by any of the primary studies. Housing is a universal human right (United Nations, 1948; UN General Assembly, 1966). Thus, our study underlines the growing need for housing to supply affordable housing for populations and younger generations, especially in response to the worldwide spread of funding movements by populist and nationalist politics.

Turkey Example

the real change in the Hedonic Housing Price Index (HKFE) prepared by the CBRT following the housing sales and building permit statistics, it is seen that the index increased by approximately 25% in real terms between 2010 and 2018. This varies regionally. For example, while the real housing price increase is 72% in Istanbul, it is 53 % in İzmir and 50% in the

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region where Aydın, Denizli and Muğla take the second place .¹Housing prices also decreased in regions other than the TR C1 region, where the rate of increase in the Southeast Anatolian region is higher than the Turkey average. It is seen that the increase in Turkey is higher than both the OECD average and the Euro area. While the price/rent index in the Euro area decreased during the period, it increased by 7% in the OECD area. It is also interesting that the increase in Turkey was 30%. When looking at individual countries, the biggest increase in the index is in Canada with 42%, while Turkey (30%) Sweden (38%) and Israel (33%) are the 4th countries in the index (OECD, 2018). The biggest decline is in Russia with 55%, followed by Estonia, Latvia, Italy and Greece, respectively.

Based on General Literature Scans

After working with various search engines (ECOLITIT IN EBSCOHOST, GOOGLE SCOSOS, SCOPUS, SCOPISTIRECT) the search terms of other databases appear to contain various combinations of the following keywords: '*immigrant*', '*immigration*', '*house price*', '*housing price*' , '*Property value*', '*rents*', '*housing market*', '*urban housing*'.

In addition, when the reference sections and earlier comments of all empirical studies are searched, both published and unpublished studies are increasing rapidly. It is also true that analysis of published studies is also mandatory for unpublished studies in this field and updated version of working papers.

¹ In the TR 61 (Antalya, Burdur, Isparta), Antalya), TR C1 (Kilis, Adıyaman, Gaziantep), TR 62 (Adana, Mersin) sub-regions, the increase in the real house price index seems to be higher than the country average. Except for the TR 82 (Çankırı, Kastamonu, Sinop) and TR A1 (Erzurum, Erzincan, Bayburt) sub-regions, housing prices have decreased in the entire Black Sea and Eastern Anatolia region.

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Foresight

Partial

Figure 2: Funnel plot correlation of partial correlations, immigration and house prices; reflects heterogeneity among results that are almost symmetrically distributed around zero .

When the two graphs presented above are evaluated together, while Turkey is considered as a country where there is a rapid increase in the real housing price index, the result is that the increase in the price/rent index is above the real housing price increase. According to this table, based on the view that housing investments are subject to an increase in the return period, it can be concluded that housing prices are higher than the increase in rents, which shows the temporary use value of the house.

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Figure 2. *Immigrants and house prices. Scatter diagrams show the correlation between the immigrant share of the population as of 2005 and the percentage change in house prices over the next ten years, (2005-2015). Migration is delayed overcoming its potential reverse causation. Panel A covers most OECD countries. Panel B covers the 14 countries covered by our meta-regression analysis.*

Housing price data is sourced from the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) (2018). Table 1 reports the BIS percentage change in real house prices from 10 years to 2015-15. Examples of world rankings show that BIS data for Spanish house prices date back to 2005Q4. To ensure a consistent comparison of prices, they adopted this index of home price growth for the last 4 months of 2015 for all countries over the decade. Prices are decided and intervened by the CPI (BIS, 2018).

The purpose of this section, which includes descriptive statistics, is not to distribute the focus of the thesis, but only the general view of the sector in the economy, and the housing prices show an increase in real terms in Turkey between 2010 and 2018, based on the general view of the sector. In other words, it is obvious that it supplied a better return than most of the traditional financial investment instruments as an investment tool during the period.

Housing Problem in Research on Syrian Refugees

The influx of refugees/asylum seekers, which appeared after the civil war that started in the Syrian Arab Republic in 2011, has created many new economic, social and cultural problems in countries where immigration is concentrated. For this reason, there has been an increase in the results with the support of the institutions funding academic research in this field. Considering the focus of research on Syrian refugees, humanitarian aid includes issues such as access to public services, as well as integration into the labor market. It is a fact that the connection between developments in the housing market and macroeconomics is based on both theoretical and empirical research within the field of urban economy, financial economics and macroeconomics. According to these findings, it can be said that the studies based on regional or inter-country comparisons show that housing prices are sensitive to economic cycles and affect variables such as income surplus, industrial production and employment. Because Hilbers et al. , who examined the structure of the housing market in Europe . (2008) groups the tools that affect housing prices as taxes on housing, incentive mechanisms, monetary policy (interest rate), structural supply and demand factors, and housing finance policy, because of the situations we have summarized above.

Expected and Permanent Income Element

Meen (2002) looking at the long-term determinants of house prices , expressed expected and permanent income as important explainers with a separate characterization. The average age and structural distribution of the population, as key factors, are the factors that decide the user costs, the interest rate, the housing tax rates and the expected return on investment of the housing. Similarly, Reichert (1990) , who analyzed the determinants of housing prices with quarterly data over a 12-year period, found interrelated concepts. The subject of changes in the

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population structure, which we can define as variables, gives the result that the level of employment and permanent income are the most influential variables on housing prices.

Chart 1: Country distribution of estimates and weighted average impact²

Country	Immigrant % population 2015 (one)	house price Percentage of change in ten years to 2015 (2nd)	Percentage of natives who do not want to live with immigrants (3)	Number of trials [estimates] (4)	WLS weighted average (5)	95% CI (6)
all	19.2117.71		14.25	45 [474]	0.008	0.002; 0.015
USA	14.49-23.52		13.60	7 [34]	-0.001	-0.010; 0.008
Spain	12.69-30.62		7.50	6 [71]	0.111	0.024; 0.198
Canada	21.8043.66		4.10	6 [65]	0.006	0.004; 0.007
Britain	13.200.51		14.20	5 [109]	-0.042	-0.091; 0.006
Australia	28.2237.35		10.50	5 [16]	0.018	0.008; 0.029
Switzerland	29.3938.29		6.90	4 [68]	0.029	-0.013; 0.072
New Zealand	22.9629.41		5.90	3 [60]	-0.076	-0.256; 0.105
all others	18.0321.31		23.53	9 [46]	0.030	0.014; 0.047

For example, in terms of cities with dense population, according to Jud and Winkler (2002), real housing price increases are affected by population growth, changes in real income,

²Column (1) reports the housing situation of immigrants as a share of the population as of 2015. Column (2) reports the total percentage change in real house prices from 10 years to 2015. Column (3) does not report the percentage of locals, which appears to be a preference for living next to immigrants. Column (4) reports the number of runs and estimates in square brackets. Column (5) reports the weighted least squares weighted average, adjusted standard errors for aggregation of estimates within studies. Column (6) reports the 95% confidence intervals. All other include Belgium, Iceland, Israel, Italy, Singapore, South Africa, and Sweden.

Sources: Column (1), World Bank (2012). Column (2), Bank for International Settlements (2018). Column (3), World Value Surveys, Miscellaneous Topics.

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construction costs and interest rates. Especially in the literature review part of our study, if they meet three criteria, they were included in the meta-analysis. First, we reported an estimate of the impact of immigration on house prices, and second, we included controlling for various other factors that affect house prices. Based on this, the conversion of the table and data below into a formula is of a summary nature.

The study had to report sample sizes and an outcome statistic, such as a t-statistic or a p-value that could be converted into a partial correlation. Partial correlations show that t is a statistical degree and df work. It is expressed by where it differs $\sqrt{t^2 + df}$

. In terms of result values in all studies, migration (M) and housing prices (P) also represent vector variables with coordination.

Chart 2: On the impact of immigration on house prices meta-regression estimates

	Basic estimates (one)	Regional expressions (2nd)	With country expressions (3)
Still	0.039 (4.53)***	0.040 (2.98)***	0.239 (2.59)**
Standard error	0.139 (0.29)	0.278 (0.57)	1,202 (2.99)***
Attitude towards immigrants	-0.004 (-3.43)***	-0.004 (-2.94)***	-0.024 (-2.59)**
average year	0.001 (1.81)*	0.001 (1.52)	0.001 (2.87)***
IV	0.026 (2.06)**	0.026 (1.96)*	0.011 (1.20)
Income	0.032 (2.26)**	0.028 (2.00)*	0.033 (2.05)**
Bank interest _	0.098 (0.74)	0.074 (0.58)	0.024 (0.23)
Parent	0.119 (1.76)*	0.119 (1.90)*	0.108 (2.98)***
Population	-0.049 (-3.01)***	-0.045 (-2.32)**	-0.026 (- 1.84)*

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<i>Stock</i>	-0.050 (-2.73)***	-0.050 (-2.78)***	-0.048 (-3.04)***
<i>Area</i>	0.087 (3.46)***	0.083 (3.21)***	0.082 (1.85)*
<i>Nation</i>	0.008 (0.41)	0.078 (1.81)*	0.031 (0.29)
<i>Local</i>	NO	YES	NO
<i>As a country</i>	NO	NO	YES
<i>adjusted R2 - n (k)</i>	0.24 40 (444)	0.29 40 (444)	0.39 40 (444)

Notes: Column (1) is the baseline results. Regional data is added to Column (2) and country data to Column (3). All models were estimated using unconstrained weighted least squares using inverse variance weights. And n and k represent the number of searches and the number of estimates, respectively. The base in columns (2) and (3) are North America and the USA, respectively. Parentheses report t -statistics using standard errors adjusted for clustering estimates within studies. For Attitudes Towards Migrants, 5 studies and 30 observations were lost due to missing observations. *, **, *** denote statistical significance at 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively.

$$P_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 M_{it} + \alpha_z z_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}^3$$

I and t indices express substitution times with period t .

While models are estimated with different estimation methods in the literature, housing demand is expressed as a function of financial and financial indicators of demographic characteristics, as well as many features of income.

Conclusion

One concern with meta-regressions is that attitudes towards immigrants are affected by immigration, meaning attitudes may be endogenous. For example, if attitudes are affected by the effect of immigration on house prices, this may bias the weighted least squares parameter

³House price data is sourced from the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) (2018). Table 1 column (2) reports the BIS percentage change in real home prices for 10 years, up to 2015-15. For example, BIS data for house prices for Spain date back to Q4 2005. To ensure a consistent comparison of prices, it was decided to use ten-year home price growth up to Q4 2015 for all countries. Prices are stabilized by CPI (BIS, 2018).

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estimates. The main difference is that the coefficient of attitudes towards immigrants is smaller, although it is still statistically and practically significant. The other difference is that the sign in the average year changes from positive to negative. In summary, our findings show that negative attitudes towards immigrants can offset the demand effect on housing prices resulting from the increasing population. This is consistent with emigration because of immigration, or a decrease in the comfort value of a place, leading to a reduced willingness to pay higher house prices. It is seen that even the behavioral qualities we obtained in our findings guide the selection process for housing destinations (Edin et al., 2003; Saiz and Wachter, 2011). The tendency of new immigrants to live in the same areas as earlier generations of immigrants, combined with the reluctance of residents with negative attitudes towards immigration to live near immigrants, weakens the relationship between immigration and housing prices.

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